

Predicting Durability of Precast Concrete Blocks via Resistivity and Sorptivity

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Abstract:

Sorptivity is a key parameter for assessing capillary water absorption and concrete durability. In this study, sorptivity for six concrete mixtures was measured according to ASTM C1585, and electrical surface resistivity was measured on companion specimens according to AASHTO T 358 using a four-point Wenner probe. Initial sorptivity values were derived from cumulative water absorption versus the square root of time and compared with resistivity results. The mixtures showed clear differences in transport behavior. Mix 6 had the highest initial sorptivity ($S_i = 0.03622 \text{ mm/s}^{0.5}$) and the lowest resistivity ($13.23 \text{ k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$), whereas Mix 1 had the highest resistivity ($30.38 \text{ k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$) and lower sorptivity. An inverse correlation was observed between surface resistivity and initial sorptivity ($R^2 = 0.78$; $\text{RMSE} = 12.4\%$), indicating that concretes with greater capillary absorption tend to have lower electrical resistivity because of a more interconnected pore structure. Overall, surface resistivity is a useful complementary indicator of sorptivity-based transport behavior.

Keywords: Sorptivity; Surface resistivity; Capillary water absorption; Durability

1. INTRODUCTION

Sorptivity is a key transport parameter that quantifies the rate of capillary water absorption in unsaturated cementitious materials. It is widely used as an indicator of durability because water acts as the primary carrier of aggressive agents that contribute to concrete deterioration. Sorptivity is commonly measured using ASTM C1585, in which cumulative water uptake is plotted against the square root of time to determine initial and secondary absorption. Previous studies have shown that sorptivity is strongly influenced by pore structure, pore connectivity, and moisture transport mechanisms, making it a useful metric for comparing the durability-related performance of concrete mixtures. However, the ASTM C1585 procedure is labor-intensive and time-consuming, which has increased interest in faster and more automated methods for evaluating sorptivity and related transport behavior.

Recent studies have improved the understanding of sorptivity from both experimental and mechanistic perspectives. Strong correlations between ASTM C1585 initial sorptivity and contact-angle-based wetting parameters suggest that surface wettability may provide a rapid indicator of capillary absorption behavior (Kabir and Garg, 2023). In addition, a computer-vision-based method has been developed to automatically track water uptake and predict both initial and secondary sorptivity with high accuracy, offering a low-cost alternative to repeated manual mass measurements (Kabir et al., 2024). At the material scale, the pore structure of coarse aggregate has been shown to significantly affect concrete pore structure and water absorption. Aggregates with critical pore diameters larger than those of the surrounding mortar increased the initial water sorption rate and accelerated the transition from initial to secondary sorption (Shankaramurthy et al., 2025). Furthermore, long-term imbibition has been shown to include distinct primary and secondary periods associated with capillary flow and slower diffusion-related processes in finer pores (Alderete et al., 2020). Collectively, these findings show that sorptivity is influenced by mixture composition, pore connectivity, surface characteristics, aggregate pore features, and long-term moisture redistribution mechanisms.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

Six mixtures were evaluated in this study to represent a range of concrete materials and products (Figure 1). Mix 1 had a water-to-cement ratio of 0.35, Mix 2 represented architectural concrete, and Mixes 3-6 had water-to-cementitious ratios of 0.45, 0.55, 0.65, and 0.75, respectively.

2.2. ASTM C1585 Sorptivity

The sorptivity of the investigated concrete mixtures was determined in accordance with ASTM C1585. Specimens were prepared by cutting the original elements into nominal 50 mm × 50 mm × 50 mm cubes. Before testing, the specimens were conditioned to achieve a consistent unsaturated internal moisture state. To ensure unidirectional water ingress, all faces except the designated test face were sealed. Each specimen was then placed with the exposed face in contact with water at the immersion depth specified by the standard. Specimen mass was recorded at selected time intervals after excess surface water was removed. The cumulative volume of absorbed water per unit exposed area was calculated from the measured mass increase, and the sorptivity index was determined from the slope of the absorption curve plotted against the

square root of time. The initial slope was defined as the initial sorptivity, and the secondary slope as the secondary sorptivity of the concrete mixture.

2.2. AASHTO T 358 surface resistivity test

The electrical surface resistivity of the concrete specimens was measured in accordance with AASHTO T 358 using a four-electrode Wenner probe. Measurements were taken at multiple locations on each specimen. Before testing, the specimens were immersed in water for 24 hours to achieve 100% relative humidity. The recorded resistivity values were averaged first at the specimen level and then at the mixture level. Surface resistivity was used as a nondestructive indicator of pore structure connectivity and the concrete's potential resistance to fluid and ionic transport. The measured resistivity values were also compared with the initial sorptivity results to evaluate the relationship between electrical resistivity and the capillary absorption behavior of the investigated concrete mixtures.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The sorptivity results showed clear differences in capillary absorption among the investigated concrete mixtures (Figure 1). Mix 6 exhibited the highest initial sorptivity ($S_i = 0.03622 \text{ mm/s}^{0.5}$), followed by Mixes 5, 4, and 3, indicating greater early-stage water uptake in these mixtures. In contrast, Mixes 1 and 2 showed comparatively low initial sorptivity values, suggesting lower capillary suction and a denser pore structure. For all mixtures, secondary sorptivity values were lower than the corresponding initial values, consistent with the expected decline in absorption rate after the initial capillary filling period. Although Mix 6 had the highest initial sorptivity, it showed the lowest secondary sorptivity ($S_s = 0.00084 \text{ mm/s}^{0.5}$), indicating rapid early absorption followed by a markedly lower later-stage absorption rate.

Figure 1. Comparison of conventional and computer-vision-based sorptivity assessment methods. (a) ASTM C1585 sorptivity test setup and experimentally obtained plots of depth of penetration, i , versus

square root of time for Mixes 1–6, used to determine the initial and secondary sorptivity coefficients. (b) Schematic of the proposed computer-vision-based sorptivity method, showing specimen imaging, wetting-front detection, and quantification of capillary absorption depth in cementitious specimens.

The surface resistivity results showed an opposite trend (Figure 2). Mix 1 exhibited the highest average resistivity at approximately 30.38 kΩ·cm, followed by Mix 2 at 24.54 kΩ·cm. In contrast, Mix 6 showed the lowest resistivity at approximately 13.23 kΩ·cm, while Mix 5 also exhibited a relatively low value of 16.33 kΩ·cm. The remaining mixtures fell between these extremes and showed moderate resistivity values, indicating intermediate resistance to transport. In general, higher surface resistivity indicates lower ionic conductivity and a less connected pore network, whereas lower resistivity suggests greater ease of ionic movement through the concrete. These results support the sorptivity measurements by showing that mixtures with lower transport resistance tend to absorb water more rapidly.

Figure 2. Evaluation of surface resistivity and its correlation with initial sorptivity for the investigated mixtures. (a) Experimental setup for the surface resistivity test using a four-point probe. (b) Measured surface resistivity values of Mix 1 to Mix 6, shown as scatter, box, and violin plots to capture dispersion and distribution characteristics. (c) Relationship between surface resistivity and initial sorptivity, S_i , determined from ASTM C 1585 testing.

The relationship between surface resistivity and initial sorptivity further confirmed this trend. Regression analysis showed that surface resistivity decreased as initial sorptivity increased, yielding a reasonably strong inverse correlation ($R^2 = 0.78$) and an RMSE of 12.4%. This result indicates that mixtures with greater capillary water uptake generally exhibited lower electrical resistivity, consistent with a more interconnected pore structure that facilitates both water ingress and ionic transport. Although the correlation was not perfect, the relatively high coefficient of determination suggests that surface resistivity can serve as a useful complementary indicator of sorptivity-based transport behavior in concrete mixtures.

4. Conclusions and Future Work

The investigated concrete mixtures showed clear differences in sorptivity and surface resistivity, indicating variations in transport-related behavior. Mixtures with higher initial sorptivity generally exhibited lower surface resistivity, whereas those with lower sorptivity showed higher resistivity. The inverse correlation between these parameters suggests that both are strongly influenced by pore connectivity and transport continuity. Overall, the combined use of sorptivity and surface resistivity provides a practical and effective approach for evaluating the durability-related transport performance of concrete mixtures.

Future work should focus on extending the computer-vision-based sorptivity approach from cement systems to concrete specimens, as illustrated in Figure 1(b). Because concrete contains coarse aggregates and a more heterogeneous pore structure, additional validation is needed to confirm the accuracy of the method in predicting absorption behavior. Further studies should also examine a wider range of mixture compositions and relate image-based sorptivity predictions to other durability indicators, such as surface resistivity, to support broader application in concrete durability assessment.

5. REFERENCES

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